

**INTERROGATION OF THE PEOPLE'S MOVEMENTS OF 1916
(ON THE EXAMPLE OF KYRGYZ)**

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Annotation: In this work contains the text of the interrogation of witnesses of the soaring folk movements after mobilization to the labor force and the written protocol of this interrogation.

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Witness interrogation protocol

Pishpek

September 3, 1916

I am a police officer of the Pishpek City Police. On behalf of Nikanov, the head of the Pishpak uyezd, Lieutenant Colonel Niyozbek Tulin, a former translator of the district administration, questioned and testified:

I came from the nurmambet volost of the Kyrgyz. From a small place this year in the city of Verny I became a trustee to divide Nurmambet volost in two. He gladly moved to Pishpek in mid-June and remained here until August 8 of this year. Taking an order from the uyezd administration in the name of the bat District pristavi on the production of tukuz volostini, he went to the bat and went to the spy Ovul on the way, and the learned officer sent the received package to pristav. On August 10 or 11, peasants Gavrila Chivtsov, Vasily Karanukin and others came to the village of Yuryevsk (Santosh) from the village of Ivanovsk, where the honorary Kyrgyz of Nurmambetovsk and the Bayseitovsk volost were gathered. The peasants of the village of Yuryevsk asked the question of whether the Kyrgyz from the Sarbagish clan wanted to plunder the villages of Ivanovsk and Yuryevsk, and whether the Kyrgyz and Russians would guard each other so as not to escape in the event of an attack. In response to all this, part of the peasants of the village of Yuryevsk rushed to escape to different directions, some to Pyshpak, some to Ivanovsk only part or even less. I had Nikolai Denisenk (shopkeeper), Pyotr Ivanov (Miller), Osip I still had a soldier Maria (he has five children) and livestock, after the kirpva they began a street to the mountains, and then to Zagorny. the volosts rushed to the villages of Choriyeusk (for things) to plunder, after which I, at Maria's request, sent my brother Joseph Tulin with Maria to bring things to the village of Yuryevskoye. 40 peasants went to the village of Yuryevsk two of them took Maria's children from me .

According to the father of the peasants, the bat commanders said that boiling could not come and go to the bat. Then that day I went to the bailiff with a package to report that the Kyrgyz would take over the abandoned villages of the peasants and rob them. Before I arrived, three Kyrgyz welcomed me and took me to the Kegeti highway, where Kanat Abukin stood. He asked me where I went, I said that I went to the bailiff with an election package. Then Kanat took the package in my portfolio and all the papers. Kanat Abukin said that he was elected Khan, and whoever did not obey him was beheaded. China said that it has a connection with Turkey, the Afghans and troops will come from them, with whom they will take Russia, and this Russia will no longer exist. After that, the sash attacked the bat several times. He had a lot of people, his troops were up to 5,000. Abaidinsk is within the volosts of Temirbulatovsk, Shamurzinsk, Shamsinsk, Nurmambetovsk, Bayseitovsk and Itigatinsk.

The Kanat was very rude to the Kyrgyz, drove them away, was forced to oppose the Russian army, they did not obey, punished with the court, that is, cut off the head. For example, the Kyrgyz abukin rope cut off the head of a Kyrgyz in Temirbulatov volost, since it did not oppose the Russians, after which the Kyrgyz of Temirbulatov volost left, that is, they fled through the mountains. The Kanat then led his detachment through the mountains behind the fleeing Kyrgyz (blacksmiths). In the Ram Valley, he again collected escaped Kyrgyz, sent part of the Kyrgyz to the bat again with his brother Baydala Abukin, and part of the Kyrgyz drove to Karagu (the village of Stolypnsk), the Kanat itself. A few days there he surrounded Stolypnsk. Then the Russian army from Norin arrived in Karagu. The Kyrgyz moved to Susk, that is, rushed to run. The wing again gathered the entire Kyrgyz and forced them to move to the karakul Valley, where the madrasah was located. At that time, about two hundred more Cossacks arrived. All the Kyrgyz began to run to different mountains, the Kyrgyz said that the Kanat was killed. More said who ran away. We took advantage of this opportunity to escape, namely Nurmambetovilar. Isytatins and Bayseitovsk, who are now sitting in Sousamyr. I ask you to interrogate the peasants indicated in this protocol, who can confirm that I did not walk around with relatives in 19 wagons .

They were guys against their will, and I saw them in an avalanche, where I came to them, along with me and other Kyrgyz of the same volost, fled to the Suusamir, where I now stand. The peasants who guarded me promised to inform the authorities about me, I will tell you my honor, I ate Russian bread, I did not

think to go against the government. Of course, one in the field is not a warrior.
Taken by the sash, so I ask you to recognize me as innocent .

August 30, 1916

The city of Pishpek.

Retired provincial secretary

Niyozbek Tulin

Careless regional secretary, I add that I had to leave 7 young children with my
wife in Suusamir, they are dying of hunger.

N.Tulin

Received instruction by police officer Nikonov

Witness interrogation protocol

October 28, 1916

Pishpek District 6 judge questioned persons who were listed as witnesses
based on Article 443. The detection of criminal proceedings and the testimony of
the interrogated persons: Dyura Saurambaev, 52 years old, tynaevsky governor
of volost, I live in my volost, a Muslim, I have not appealed to the court.

The first August of this year. On the territory of the Red River, from 18
versts in the city of Tokmak, a meeting of honorary persons of the tynaev volost
was held to discuss ways and methods of compiling a list of workers who must
be provided to work behind the army in the field.

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